

Thermodynamics of the Interaction of Bivalent Transition Metal Ions with Phthalanilic Acids

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The thermodynamic stepwise stability constants, free energy, enthalpy and entropy changes for the formation of Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} ions with phthalanilic, 4-methylphthalanilic, 4-methoxyphthalanilic, 4-chlorophthalanilic, 4-bromophthalanilic and 4-nitrophthalanilic acids were determined. Analysis of the data indicated the chelation of phthalanilic acids through nitrogen of secondary amide and carboxylate groups.

AMINO-ACIDS with oxygen and nitrogen donor atoms have been greatly used as ligands in carrying out the thermodynamical studies on their metal complexes perhaps because of their biological importance¹⁻³, and for finding out the number and strength of bonds and to detect concomitant changes in the structure of the complexes⁷⁻¹⁰. Anilic acids also have the same donor sites but no reference is available on such type of studies with these compounds. The present communication deals with the determinations of thermodynamical stability constants, ΔF , ΔH and ΔS for the interaction of Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with phthalanilic, 4-methylphthalanilic, 4-methoxyphthalanilic, 4-chlorophthalanilic, 4-bromophthalanilic and 4-nitrophthalanilic acids.

Experimental

The experimental set up and methods have been described earlier^{9,10}. The measured pH values, calibrated from the analytical concentration of perchloric acid and activity coefficient of H^+ , agreed¹¹ within ± 0.004 pH units. The accuracy of the instrument was ± 0.02 units. Carbon dioxide free nitrogen presaturated with solvent methanol-water mixture (20%, v/v), was continuously bubbled through the solution to provide an inert atmosphere.

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade, methanol was purified by the standard method¹². Phthalanilic acids were prepared by the reported method¹³ and recrystallised from ethanol. The solutions of metal chlorides, ferrous perchlorates, perchloric acid, sodium perchlorate and anilic acids were prepared in methanol-water mixture (20%, v/v). Due allowance for the contraction in volume on mixing the two solvents were made^{14,15}.

Calculations: The thermodynamic proton-ligand dissociation constants of phthalanilic acids and stability constants of their complexes were

determined potentiometrically following the Bjerrum-Calvin titration technique^{16,17} as adapted by Irving and Rossotti¹⁸, and employing the correction factors introduced by Van Uitert¹⁹. The enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) changes were calculated from the temperature coefficient of the equilibrium constant in a medium of 0.1 M $NaClO_4$. The calculations were made on DEC-2050 digital computer.

The accuracy of pK values of acids and $\log K$ values of the complexes is ± 0.02 and ± 0.04 log units, respectively. Therefore, the precisions of ΔH and ΔS are ± 0.56 kcal mol^{-1} and ± 2.4 cal $mol^{-1} deg^{-1}$, respectively.

Results and Discussion

The values of pK_1 and pK_2 corresponding to the deprotonation of $COOH$ and NH at 22, 30 and 40°, respectively and at ionic strength 0.1 M $NaClO_4$ are given in Table 1. The values of formation

TABLE 1—PROTONATION CONSTANTS OF PHTHALANILIC ACIDS IN 0.1 M $NaClO_4$, AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Acids	Temp. °C	pK_1	pK_2
P	22	4.35	11.15
	30	4.25	11.10
	40	4.15	10.90
4-methyl-P	22	4.45	11.30
	30	4.38	11.15
	40	4.33	11.00
4-methoxy-P	22	4.42	11.30
	30	4.37	11.13
	40	4.33	11.00
4-bromo-P	22	4.15	11.15
	30	4.10	11.00
	40	4.00	10.88
4-chloro-P	22	4.10	11.10
	30	4.00	10.95
	40	3.90	10.85
4-nitro-P	22	3.80	10.90
	30	3.65	10.85
	40	3.55	10.70

P = Phthalanilic acid.

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TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC STABILITY CONSTANTS OF METAL COMPLEXES OF PHTHALANILIC ACIDS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Acids	Formation constants	Temp.	Mn ^{II}	Fe ^{II}	Co ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}
P	Log T _{K₁}	22	5.30	10.90	5.40	5.25	8.30
		30	5.25	10.70	5.35	5.20	8.15
		40	5.15	10.45	5.25	5.10	8.00
	Log T _{K₂}	22	4.55	7.75	4.55	4.45	7.25
		30	4.50	7.65	4.50	4.40	7.20
		40	4.45	7.55	4.45	4.35	7.10
	Log Tβ ₂	22	9.85	18.65	9.95	9.70	15.55
		30	9.75	18.35	9.85	9.60	15.35
		40	9.60	18.00	9.70	9.45	15.10
4-methyl-P	Log T _{K₁}	22	6.40	11.95	6.85	7.50	9.25
		30	6.30	11.65	6.75	7.40	9.00
		40	6.20	11.35	6.65	7.25	8.80
	Log T _{K₂}	22	5.15	9.85	5.20	5.65	7.90
		30	5.10	9.20	5.15	5.60	7.80
		40	5.05	9.05	5.10	5.50	7.70
	Log Tβ ₂	22	11.55	21.30	12.05	13.15	17.15
		30	11.40	20.85	11.90	13.00	16.80
		40	11.25	20.40	11.75	12.75	16.50
4-methoxy-P	Log T _{K₁}	22	7.65	10.80	8.60	8.60	9.65
		30	7.55	10.50	8.45	8.45	9.40
		40	7.45	10.20	8.30	8.30	9.15
	Log T _{K₂}	22	5.50	9.60	6.40	6.40	7.75
		30	5.45	9.40	6.30	6.30	7.60
		40	5.40	9.20	6.20	6.20	7.45
	Log Tβ ₂	22	13.15	20.40	15.00	15.00	17.40
		30	13.00	19.90	14.75	14.75	17.00
		40	12.85	19.40	14.50	14.50	16.60
4-chloro-P	Log T _{K₁}	22	6.40	11.20	7.40	7.50	9.80
		30	6.35	10.95	7.30	7.40	9.60
		40	6.25	10.70	7.20	7.25	9.35
	Log T _{K₂}	22	4.45	8.15	5.10	5.20	8.15
		30	4.40	8.00	5.05	5.15	8.05
		40	4.35	7.85	5.00	5.05	7.95
	Log Tβ ₂	22	10.85	19.35	12.50	12.70	17.95
		30	10.75	18.95	12.35	12.55	17.65
		40	10.70	18.55	12.20	12.30	17.30
4-bromo-P	Log T _{K₁}	22	6.45	11.20	7.40	7.55	9.30
		30	6.35	11.00	7.30	7.45	9.15
		40	6.25	10.75	7.20	7.35	9.00
	Log T _{K₂}	22	4.80	8.40	5.40	5.50	8.05
		30	4.75	8.25	5.35	5.45	7.95
		40	4.70	8.10	5.30	5.40	7.85
	Log Tβ ₂	22	11.25	19.60	12.80	13.05	17.35
		30	11.10	19.25	12.65	12.90	17.10
		40	10.95	18.85	12.50	12.75	16.85
4-nitro-P	Log T _{K₁}	22	6.60	11.95	7.05	6.60	8.75
		30	6.55	11.65	6.95	6.50	8.55
		40	6.45	11.35	6.85	6.40	8.35
	Log T _{K₂}	22	5.30	8.80	5.60	5.50	7.45
		30	5.25	8.65	5.55	5.45	7.30
		40	5.20	8.50	5.50	5.40	7.15
	Log Tβ ₂	22	11.90	20.75	12.65	12.10	16.20
		30	11.80	20.30	12.50	11.95	15.85
		40	11.65	19.85	12.35	11.80	15.50

P = Phthalanilic acid.

constants are given in Table 2 and the values of ΔF, ΔH and ΔS corresponding to first, and second step reactions are given in Table 3. The pK₁ and pK₂ were found to have the following order.

Thus the deprotonation of COOH and NH is affected by inductive and mesomeric effects of the

TABLE 3—Stepwise ΔF° at 22° and ΔH Values (kcal mole⁻¹), and ΔS Values in (cal mol⁻¹ deg⁻¹) at 30°

Acids	Thermo-dynamic parameter	Mn ^{II}	Fe ^{II}	Co ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}
P	-ΔF ₁ ⁰	29.50	61.00	30.12	29.25	46.33
	-ΔF ₂ ⁰	26.44	44.22	26.44	25.52	41.30
	-ΔH ₁	10.54	46.65	12.30	12.30	29.75
	-ΔH ₂	9.58	26.40	9.87	9.87	16.86
	ΔS ₁	64.22	39.62	60.33	57.45	55.94
	ΔS ₂	57.03	60.88	56.07	53.18	82.72
4-methyl-P	-ΔF ₁ ⁰	35.61	66.99	37.87	41.92	51.97
	-ΔF ₂ ⁰	29.37	53.26	29.96	32.76	45.19
	-ΔH ₁	17.95	60.38	18.24	24.10	42.55
	-ΔH ₂	13.39	32.80	13.69	14.73	19.16
	ΔS ₁	59.79	22.22	66.27	60.50	31.46
	ΔS ₂	53.97	69.45	54.98	61.04	88.24
4-methoxy-P	-ΔF ₁ ⁰	42.59	60.46	47.78	47.74	53.68
	-ΔF ₂ ⁰	31.34	54.52	36.74	36.11	44.64
	-ΔH ₁	18.37	53.60	25.52	27.36	49.62
	-ΔH ₂	11.59	33.05	16.23	14.94	26.90
	ΔS ₁	82.01	22.64	75.40	69.04	13.51
	ΔS ₂	86.82	72.34	69.33	71.25	60.21
4-chloro-P	-ΔF ₁ ⁰	35.86	62.51	41.00	41.55	54.68
	-ΔF ₂ ⁰	26.11	46.44	29.20	29.33	46.48
	-ΔH ₁	15.52	49.33	21.00	22.97	42.89
	-ΔH ₂	9.58	28.70	10.54	12.30	22.59
	ΔS ₁	68.78	44.60	67.78	62.97	39.75
	ΔS ₂	55.94	59.91	63.26	59.37	80.92
4-bromo-P	-ΔF ₁ ⁰	36.11	62.80	41.95	41.80	52.09
	-ΔF ₂ ⁰	27.49	47.91	30.88	31.51	44.86
	-ΔH ₁	14.73	51.42	15.94	18.24	31.21
	-ΔH ₂	8.49	30.63	8.49	10.54	18.37
	ΔS ₁	72.34	38.37	85.77	79.96	70.71
	ΔS ₂	64.48	58.41	75.94	71.13	89.62
4-nitro-P	-ΔF ₁ ⁰	36.82	66.99	39.33	36.74	48.70
	-ΔF ₂ ⁰	30.21	50.38	31.34	31.51	42.63
	-ΔH ₁	15.31	57.20	13.33	17.74	39.75
	-ΔH ₂	7.99	31.71	12.30	9.87	24.98
	ΔS ₁	72.93	32.72	71.13	64.35	30.25
	ΔS ₂	75.27	63.20	66.27	73.30	59.79

P = Phthalanilic acid.

substituents. The electron density at the reaction centre is reduced by the electron attracting groups in the order, NO₂ > Cl > Br. Hence, the liberation of the proton becomes easier in the same order while reverse is true in 4-methyl and 4-methoxy derivatives.

The presence of polynuclear species could be ruled out on the basis of formation curves determined from the ligand metal ratio of 5 : 1 and 10 : 1 which were found to be identical. The highest value of $\bar{n} \approx 2$ (average number of ligands attached per metal ion) indicated the combining ratio of metal to ligand as 1 : 2. The formation constants were in the order

The higher value of Fe^{II} complexes may be attributed to the higher value of CFSE of the metal ion in a strong ligand field. Such higher values are reported in the case of riboflavin, o-phenanthroline and folic acid²⁰. Nitro group is a stronger σ and π electron acceptor and hence in the complexes of

4-nitrophthalanic acids, the cation is less destabilised as compared to the proton. Methoxy group increases the electron density at the reaction centre and hence increases the stability of the chelate. A straight line obtained in between the values of $\log K_1$ and ionisation potentials of the metal ions indicate that the formation of the first complex species is directly proportional to the ionisation potential of the central metal ion. Fe^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes were the exceptions which may be due to higher CFSE and Jahn-Teller effect, respectively.

The values of entropy changes are very high which may be due to the negative charge on the coordinating sites which brings about a shielding of central dipositive metal ion from exercising its orienting influence on the unfrozen distant water dipoles²¹. The electrostatic interaction also has an endothermic effect on the heats of reaction²². The contribution to the total change in enthalpy by metal-carboxylate bond is generally very small. The exothermic values given in each case are fairly high and can not be accounted by metal-oxygen bond only. This indicates the involvement of nitrogen atom in coordination.

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